

A new name and two new combinations in *Leucheria* Lag. (Asteraceae; Nassauvieae)

Mark A. Hershkovitz *

Isla Negra, Chile.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 22(01), 764–765

Publication history: Received on 08 March 2024; revised on 13 April 2024; accepted on 16 April 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.22.1.1180>

Abstract

Molecular phylogenetic analysis has demonstrated that *Polyachyrus* Lag. species must be reclassified in *Leucheria* Lag. Here, *Polyachyrus cinereus* Ricardi & Weltdt is renamed as *Leucheria duraniorum*, and *Polyachyrus gayi* J.Rémy and *Polyachyrus poeppigii* Kunze ex Less. subsp. *multifidis* (D.Don) Ricardi & Weltdt are recombined in *Leucheria*.

Keywords: *Leucheria*; *Polyachyrus*; Nassauvieae; Asteraceae

1. Introduction

Hershkovitz [1] published a molecular phylogenetic analysis of species of the flowering plant genus *Leucheria* Lag. and related Nassauvieae (Asteraceae). That analysis demonstrated that the small genus *Polyachyrus* Lag. is phylogenetically nested within *Leucheria*. These generic names were published simultaneously in the same work [2], and neither ever had been considered a synonym of the other, hence neither has inherent priority per the ICN [3]. Hershkovitz thus transferred the species of the smaller genus, *Polyachyrus*, to the much larger one, *Leucheria*. However, Hershkovitz failed to appreciate that *Leucheria cinerea* (Ricardi & Weltdt) Hershk., nom. inval. per Art. 53 of [3] (\equiv *Polyachyrus cinereus* Ricardi & Weltdt) was a homonym of *L. cinerea* D. Don, which is considered to be a taxonomic synonym of *Leucheria tomentosa* (Less.) Crisci [4]. Hershkovitz also failed to provide a new combinations for *Polyachyrus gayi* J.Rémy and an accepted subspecies of *Leucheria poeppigii* (Kunze ex Less.) Hershk. In this work, *Polyachyrus cinereus* is renamed and *P. gayi* and *P. poeppigii* Kunze ex Less. subsp. *multifidis* (D.Don) Ricardi & Weltdt are recombined in *Leucheria*.

2. Methodology

The new botanical names are constructed according to the rules and conventions of the ICN [3].

3. Results and discussion

The new names are constructed per ICN rules and conventions [3] as follows:

- ***Leucheria duraniorum*** Hershk., nom. nov. BASIONYM: *Polyachyrus cinereus* Ricardi & Weltdt, Gayana, Bot. ~~no.~~ 26: 26. 1974.
- **Etymology:** The epithet honors the family of Dr. José Elias Durán Lima and his wife, Susana Yolanda Roa Ferreira, without whose support my discovery of the relations of *Polyachyrus* would not have been possible (see also [1]).
- ***Leucheria gayi*** (J.Rémy) Hershk., comb. nov. BASIONYM: *Polyachyrus gayi* J.Rémy, Fl. Chil. [Gay] 3(3): 372. 1848.

* Corresponding author: Mark A. Hershkovitz

- *Leucheria poeppigii* (Kunze ex Less.) Hershk. subsp. ***multifida*** (D.Don) Hershk., comb. nov. BASIONYM: *Polyachyrus poeppigii* Kunze ex Less. subsp. *multifidis* (D.Don) Ricardi & Weldt, Gayana Bot. 26: 19. 1974.

The new botanical names are constructed above because Hershkovitz [1] demonstrated that the taxa must be classified in the genus *Leucheria* rather than *Polyachyrus*. No combinations for these taxa had existed in the genus *Leucheria*, hence their renaming was necessary. Without effective publication per [3], the taxa may exist in nature but they do not exist for purposes of scientific communication or legally for purposes of biodiversity administration, or they exist but are incorrectly classified.

4. Conclusion

Effective publication of botanical names per ICN is essential to science. By effectively publishing here new names for three taxa of *Leucheria*, these names become available for purposes of scientific research.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Hershkovitz, MA. *Leucheria* Lag. includes *Polyachyrus* Lag. (Asteraceae; Nassauvieae), International Journal of Science, Development and Research, 2024 Apr; 9(4) : 636-646.
- [2] Lagasca, M. *Amenidades Naturales de las Españas o Bien Disertaciones Varias sobre las Producciones Naturales Espontáneas, o Conaturalizadas en los Dominios Españoles*, volume 1, 1811, Orihuela, Spain: Spain; 1811.
- [3] Turland NJ, Wiersema JH, Barrie FR, Greuter W, Hawksworth DL, Herendeen PS, Knapp S, Kusber WH, Li D-Z, Marhold K, May TW, McNeill J, Monro AM, Prado J, Price MJ, Smith GF. International Code of Nomenclature for Algae, Fungi, and Plants (Shenzhen Code) adopted by the Nineteenth International Botanical Congress Shenzhen, China, July 2017. *Regnum Vegetabile* 159. Glashütten, Germany: Koeltz Botanical Books; 2018.
- [4] Katinas L, Apodaca MJ, Crisci JV. *A synopsis of Leucheria* (Asteraceae, Nassauvieae), with notes on the morphology. Washington DC, USA: Smithsonian Scholarly Press; 2022.